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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
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**2-Global Strategic Rivalry and the Secure
Architecture: Nato's Influence on The
Formation of The International Peace, By
Yevhenii Taran. and others. p. 30.**

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GLOBAL STRATEGIC RIVALRY AND THE SECURE ARCHITECTURE: NATO'S INFLUENCE ON THE FORMATION OF THE INTERNATIONAL PEACE

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YEVHENII TARAN

PhD in Political Science, Associate Professor, Global and National Security Department, Educational and Scientific Institute of Public Administration and Civil Service, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1822-6978>

taran.evgeniy2011@gmail.com

MYKOLA TARANENKO

PhD in Law, Senior Lecturer, Department of Information, Business and Administrative Law, Faculty of Sociology and Law, National Technical University of Ukraine "Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute", Ukraine

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1594-5598>

taranenkonn@gmail.com

TETYANA KULYK

Candidate of Historical Sciences, Senior Research Officer, Associate Professor, Department of International Relations and Audit, Faculty of Finance and Economics, Dnipro University of Technology, Ukraine

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4422-7533>

Kulyk.T.V@nmu.one

ABSTRACT

This study is relevant due to the transformation of the international security environment caused by Russia's war against Ukraine, which has heightened strategic competition and underscored NATO's role in shaping the global order. The research aims to examine NATO's evolving role post-war by analyzing changes in its strategic identity, responses to geostrategic challenges, and its institutional adaptation for long-term competition. Historical and civilizational perspectives were applied to trace alliance evolution, alongside analogy methods to compare non-NATO partners, and content and case analyses to assess key developments. The findings reveal NATO's strategic transformation, the reaffirmation of its security guarantor role in the 2022 Strategic Concept, the bolstering of its eastern flank, and its efforts to counter hybrid

threats from Russia and China. A pragmatic planning model combining short-term strategies with long-term leadership goals has emerged. The study highlights the need to assess NATO's internal unity and adaptability to technological and environmental challenges.

Keywords: strategic competition, international security, NATO, Russia's war against Ukraine.

1- INTRODUCTION

In the first decades of the 21st century, the international environment has undergone profound changes accompanied by the formation of a new polycentric world order, in which internal contradictions and asymmetries in the development of key geopolitical directions are becoming more pronounced. These processes have become especially acute as a result of the Russian Federation's full-scale invasion of Ukraine, which not only posed an unprecedented challenge to the entire Euro-Atlantic security system, but also catalyzed a revision of the established mechanisms of strategic planning among leading international actors. The current stage of development of the global security architecture is characterized by increased confrontation between centers of power, growing geopolitical tensions, and intensified struggle for influence in different regions of the world¹.

Under these conditions, the activities of the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) are gaining special attention, as it is not only a key guarantor of transatlantic security but also one of the leading actors in the formation of new global strategies for deterrence and adaptation to the challenges arising from strategic competition. In response to the escalation of confrontation between the collective West, on the one hand, and authoritarian regimes led by Russia and China, on the other, NATO is forced to reconsider both its identity and the foundations of its strategic presence in the world. The focus on maintaining unity among the allies, strengthening the eastern flank of the Alliance, and building up defense capabilities are all manifestations of a new policy of deterrence and proactive security that is being formed in response to the new reality after the outbreak of the war against Ukraine².

In this context, the study of NATO's role in shaping the post-war world order is of particular relevance. First, it is about determining the security prospects for the countries of Eastern Europe, especially Ukraine, which de facto acts as an outpost of the Euro-Atlantic community. Secondly, there is a need to critically analyze new approaches to security strategy implemented in the context of strategic competition and the growing threat of global destabilization. Thirdly, it is necessary to assess the

¹ D. Kunertova and O. Schmitt, "Assessing NATO's cohesion: Methods and implications", *International Politics* (2024). DOI:10.1057/s41311-024-00641-1

² S. Rynning, *NATO: From Cold War to Ukraine, a History of the World's Most Powerful Alliance* (Yale University Press, 2024).

potential of NATO as an institution capable not only of deterring aggression, but also of playing a constructive role in shaping a new, fairer and more secure model of international relations in the post-war world.

The purpose of the study is to substantiate NATO's strategic priorities and actions to shape the new contours of the world order after the finalization of the war between Russia and Ukraine by identifying transformations in the Alliance's strategic identity.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Contemporary scholarship increasingly draws attention to the transformation of NATO's strategic thinking, its ability to adapt to new security challenges, establish cooperation with partner countries, and play a key role in maintaining and shaping the international order after active conflicts. In scientific sources, strategic competition is increasingly interpreted not only as a direct military rivalry between major geopolitical players, but also as a multifaceted interaction that covers economic, technological, ideological and information aspects, as evidenced by the works of such authors as Azubalis, and Marrone and Muti.³ The realist rationales and models presented in Bou Serhal and Alkhaja⁴, Valášek⁵ emphasize the inevitability of conflicts in a multipolar world where countries compete for dominance in strategically important regions, viewing NATO as a deterrent to states with revisionist ambitions such as Russia and China. Instead, constructivist approaches, as explored by Blessing et al.⁶ and Grgić⁷, emphasize the importance of identity, shared narratives and norms in shaping a collective security culture that helps NATO adapt to modern threats through internal reforms and institutional changes.

The analysis of the evolution of NATO's strategic doctrines allows us to trace how the organization responded to the transformation of the international security environment: from a purely defensive alliance during the Cold War to a flexible

³ A. Azubalis, *NATO and the Global South* (NATO Parliamentary Assembly, 2024), <https://www.nato-pa.int/document/2024-nato-and-global-south-report-azubalis-055-pcnp>;
A. Marrone and K. Muti, *NATO's Future: Euro-Atlantic Alliance in a Peacetime War* (Istituto Affari Internazionali, 2020).
https://www.academia.edu/44362815/NATOs_Future_Euro_Atlantic_Alliance_in_a_Peacetime_War?hb-sb-sw=45605567

⁴ G. Bou Serhal and A. Alkhaja, *Navigating the new global order: U.S. foreign policy in a multipolar era* (TRENDS Research & Advisory, 2024). <https://trendsresearch.org/insight/navigating-the-new-global-order-u-s-foreign-policy-in-a-multipolar-era/>

⁵ T. Valášek, *New perspectives on shared security: NATO's next 70 years* (Carnegie Europe, 2019). https://carnegie-production-assets.s3.amazonaws.com/static/files/NATO_int_final1.pdf

⁶ J. Blessing, K. Kjellström Elgin and N. M. Ewers-Peters, *NATO 2030: Towards a New Strategic Concept and Beyond* (Foreign Policy Institute/Henry A. Kissinger Center for Global Affairs, Johns Hopkins University SAIS, 2021). <https://sais.jhu.edu/sites/default/files/NATO2030AndBeyondAccessibleVersion.pdf>

⁷ G. Grgić, "Redefining NATO's Indo-Pacific partnerships: cooperative security meets collective defence and deterrence", *Asian Security* vol. 20, no. 1 (2024): p. 39–55. DOI:10.1080/14799855.2024.2339213

structure with a wide range of functions, as reflected in Chae⁸, Samson et al.⁹. While the 2010 Strategic Concept still held out hope for a partnership with Russia, after the annexation of Crimea in 2014, the Alliance gradually returned to a policy of deterrence, as noted by Tardy et al.¹⁰, and the Strategic Concept 2022 clearly identified Russia as the main security threat in the Euro-Atlantic region, while for the first time paying attention to the systemic challenges posed by China, which emphasizes the reorientation of geostrategic goals and the growing role of NATO as a global actor¹¹. Russia's war against Ukraine was a critical moment for the Alliance, and academic publications on the events after February 2022, such as Gheciu and von Hlatky¹² and Lo¹³, emphasize the shift from a cautious policy to an active rethinking of tasks in the fight against regimes seeking to revise the existing order. Experts in the report by Mazurkiewicz¹⁴ note that this conflict accelerated the modernization of weapons, reform of command structures, expansion of presence on the eastern flank and development of long-term support programs for Ukraine, while the issue of interoperability, standardization and integration of Ukraine into NATO defense planning has taken an important place.

Many authors emphasize that since the war, NATO has become a global security coordinator, going beyond a purely Euro-Atlantic context, as Michalski et al.¹⁵ and Tardy et al.¹⁶ argue, which is manifested not only in its military presence but also in the promotion of democratic values, the rule of law, and a transparent political culture. At the same time, it remains an open question how the Alliance will be able to balance the

⁸ H. Chae, "Impact of NATO enlargement on Eastern Europe security: Case study of Ukraine war", *Independent Study Project (ISP) Collection* (2024): 3763. https://digitalcollections.sit.edu/isp_collection/3763

⁹ P. Samson, S. Y. Kalash, N. Zivkovic, T. Forrest and B. Momani, *Scenarios of evolving global order* (Centre for International Governance Innovation, 2024). <https://www.cigionline.org/publications/scenarios-of-evolving-global-order/>

¹⁰ T. Tardy, H. Hardt, A. Pannier and C. Kasapoglu, *The nations of NATO: Shaping the alliance's relevance and cohesion* (Oxford University Press, 2022). DOI:10.1093/oso/9780192855534.001.0001

¹¹ Allied Command Transformation, "Alliances and Partnerships in a Complex and Challenging Security Environment" (NATO, 2024). <https://www.act.nato.int/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/NATO-AC24-Compendium.pdf>

¹² A. Gheciu and S. von Hlatky, "Irreconcilable Differences? NATO's Response to Russian Aggression Against Ukraine", *International Journal* vol. 79, no. 2 (2024): p. 275-296. DOI:10.1177/00207020241255999

¹³ B. Lo, *The Ukraine effect: Demise or rebirth of the global order?* (Lowy Institute, 2023). <https://www.lowyinstitute.org/publications/ukraine-effect-demise-or-rebirth-global-order>

¹⁴ A. Mazurkiewicz, *Broad and Narrow Visions of Security: Investigating the Strategic Discourse of Selected NATO Member States*. LSE Conflict and Civicness Research Group, Policy Brief, (2024). <https://peacerep.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/Broad-and-narrow-visions-of-security-Investigating-the-strategic-discourse-of-selected-NATO-member-stats-DIGITAL.pdf>

¹⁵ A. Michalski, D. Brommesson and A.-M. Ekengren, "Small states and the dilemma of geopolitics: Role change in Finland and Sweden", *International Affairs* vol. 100, no. 1 (2024): p. 139-157. DOI:10.1093/ia/iad244

¹⁶ T. Tardy, H. Hardt, A. Pannier and C. Kasapoglu, (2022). *Id.*

expansion of its global mission with the provision of the core function of collective defense, which is discussed in Brzezinski and Arick¹⁷, and some researchers, in particular Brunk and Hakimi¹⁸, warn that excessive geographical expansion may weaken the resource base and internal cohesion of the organization. A separate area of research is devoted to China's growing influence and NATO's response: The Strategic Concept 2022 for the first time identifies China as a systemic challenge, especially in areas such as technology, cybersecurity, information operations, and soft power¹⁹, although the Alliance's approach to China remains restrained due to the economic interests of individual European members, which highlights the dilemma between global engagement and regional stability in the context of competition between the United States and China.

NATO's enlargement policy, which has been actively developing since 1999, has had a significant impact on the geopolitical space of Europe, as noted by Michta²⁰, Ratti²¹, and after the war in Ukraine, the issue of Ukraine's integration or at least interoperability with the Alliance is seen as an important factor in ensuring lasting peace. In this context, cooperation with partners through new formats, such as NATO+, and flexible models of security cooperation that allow supporting countries without full membership are also explored, as described by Michaels and Sus²². At the same time, scholarship recognizes the Alliance's internal challenges in the face of strategic competition, such as the uneven distribution of financial contributions, divergent priorities among members, and the impact of populist movements, as analyzed by German and Dorman²³, Mohammadi Monfared²⁴, who emphasize that internal unity will be crucial to NATO's ability to shape a stable world order.

¹⁷ I. Brzezinski and R. Arick, *Issue brief: A NATO strategy for countering Russia* (Atlantic Council, 2025). <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/in-depth-research-reports/issue-brief/issue-brief-a-nato-strategy-for-countering-russia/>

¹⁸ I. W. Brunk and M. Hakimi, "Russia, Ukraine, and the future world order", *American Journal of International Law* vol. 116, no. 4 (2022): p. 687–697. DOI:10.1017/ajil.2022.69

¹⁹ J. Subotic, "Russia, NATO and the view from the East", *International Politics* vol. 60, no. 2 (2023): p. 259–263. DOI:10.1057/s41311-022-00415-7

²⁰ A. A. Michta, *The real reason Russia invaded Ukraine (hint: it's not NATO expansion)* (Atlantic Council, 2025). <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/new-atlanticist/the-real-reason-russia-invaded-ukraine-hint-its-not-nato-expansion/>

²¹ L. Ratti, "NATO and the CSDP after the Ukraine War: The End of European Strategic Autonomy?", *Canadian Journal of European and Russian Studies* vol. 16, no. 2 (2023): p. 73–89. DOI:10.22215/cjers.v16i2.4150

²² E. Michaels and M. Sus, "(Not) Coming of age? Unpacking the European Union's quest for strategic autonomy in security and defence", *European Security* vol. 33, no. 3 (2024): p. 383–405. DOI:10.1080/09662839.2024.2376603

²³ T. German and A. M. Dorman, "Introduction NATO at 75", *International Affairs* vol. 100, no. 2 (2024): p. 467–470. DOI:10.1093/ia/iaae063

²⁴ H. Mohammadi Monfared, "The results of the war between Russia and Ukraine in the formation of the new world order", *Strategic Discourse Quarterly* vol. 1, no. 1 (2024): p. 109–135. https://sdq.sndu.ac.ir/article_3101_a28b938aea2422d75ec92bec06e16086.pdf

Modern research clearly recognizes NATO as a key security actor that is increasingly influencing the international order through a combination of military, diplomatic and institutional instruments, and Russia's war against Ukraine has prompted a revision of the strategic vision, intensification of defense, improvement of deterrence mechanisms and transformation of the Alliance into a global force capable of operating in several regions simultaneously.

3. METHOD

The methodological basis is based on the research principles of the humanities, with the aim of comprehensively understanding the transformation of the international security environment and NATO's place in it in the context of current geopolitical challenges. The paper applies a systematic approach, whereby the US alliance relations are viewed as a complex system that unites numerous interconnected and interdependent elements, including partnerships with NATO countries and other states that play a key role in countering strategic competition, in particular, caused by Russia's aggression. For a deeper analysis of the causes of problems and shortcomings in the current system of US alliances, as well as to understand the significant differences in the nature of allied relations in different regions of the world, such as Europe, where NATO plays a leading role after the Russian-Ukrainian conflict, or other global areas, historical and civilizational approaches are used to help trace the evolution of these relations in the context of changes in the world order.

In order to identify similarities and differences between the states that have the status of the main US ally outside NATO, as well as to determine the specific features of political processes and circumstances that accompanied the involvement of individual countries in cooperation with the United States in the context of growing strategic competition after the war in Ukraine, the method of analogies is used, which allows comparing the experience of different states and their role in shaping the security environment. For a detailed analysis of the specific characteristics that shape the image of the main US non-NATO ally, such as contribution to deterring Russia or supporting the alliance's initiatives in the post-conflict world, content analysis and document analysis were used, which allowed to systematize information from official sources and identify key trends in US policy towards its partners. In addition, for an in-depth study of individual cases of granting foreign states the status of a major non-NATO ally, in particular those of strategic importance in the context of countering the Russian threat or strengthening the alliance's position, the case-study method was used, which contributed to a detailed consideration of the unique circumstances and consequences of such decisions in the broader context of shaping the world order.

4. RESULTS

4.1. TRANSFORMATION OF NATO'S STRATEGIC IDENTITY IN THE NEW GEOPOLITICAL REALITY

In the global context of strategic competition, which has intensified against the backdrop of Russia's full-scale war against Ukraine, it is of particular importance to

rethink the role of states in the global security system, as well as their interaction within interstate alliances and coalitions, such as NATO. The national strategic documents developed by each state form its foreign policy identity, as they determine the desired vision of the international order, the country's place and status in the world, its allies, competitors and opponents, as well as the resource capabilities for implementing foreign policy. However, these same processes are taking on new forms at the supranational level, where collective identity is being constructed inherent in associations of states, such as NATO, which, in fact, functions not only as a military-political alliance but also as a transnational space for the production of political and strategic meanings.

In this space, member states interact both at the level of governments and through expert and academic circles, forming a common vision of security challenges, strategic guidelines, and the future world order. NATO's collective identity is built not only through political documents or summit decisions, but also through in-depth discussions among member states, during which approaches to threat assessment are agreed upon, common interests are identified, and strategic consensus is formed. This is the essence of strategic planning in the Alliance, which is not limited to the technical documentation of priorities, but is a complex mechanism for harmonizing positions between different actors based on the practice of contestation, which increases the legitimacy of the adopted norms and decisions^{25, 26}.

The scientific and expert community plays an extremely important role in this process, as it provides the analytical and ideological basis for NATO's strategic concepts, such as the 2010 and 2022 documents, which enshrined key provisions that had long been formed on the basis of intergovernmental decisions, in particular, to deter Russian aggression, expand the Alliance's focus on China and outer space. The participation of scientists and experts in the process of shaping NATO's strategic agenda is ensured both through official channels - think tanks, specialized research support programs, advisory structures to the Secretary General of the Alliance - and through informal platforms, including international conferences, roundtables and discussion forums, among which the NATO 2030 initiative stands out. The functioning of the NATO Parliamentary Assembly is also illustrative, serving as a platform for dialogue between parliamentarians of member states and representatives of the academic community, creating a space for joint development of strategic recommendations, in particular, on updating the strategic concept. In addition, an important analytical function is performed by the Atlantic Association, which is independent of NATO and coordinates the vision of transatlantic security based on

²⁵ J. Parakilas and A. Honich (Eds.), *Strategic Commentaries: Essays about the UK, NATO, China, Russia, North Korea and Iran* (RAND Corporation, 2024). https://www.rand.org/content/dam/rand/pubs/perspectives/PEA3600/PEA3655-1/RAND_PEA3655-1.pdf

²⁶ A. Rogozińska, "The role of NATO in shaping the global security system: Reflections on the 70th anniversary of the founding of the organization", *Belügyi Szemle vol. 68*, no. (Special Issue 1) (2020): p. 35-45. DOI:10.38146/BSZ.SPEC.2020.1.3

Western values and promotes the dissemination of expert knowledge among civil society organizations in the member states²⁷.

It is the formation of NATO's strategic identity and its transformation in response to new security challenges, caused, in particular, by Russia's aggression against Ukraine, that is carried out through a constant and multilevel process of interaction between national governments, expert circles and international structures. These provisions ensure not only the Alliance's adaptation to the new geopolitical reality, but also contribute to the construction of a new model of the global order, in which NATO occupies a central place as an institution capable of political leadership, security responsibility and ideological cohesion in the post-war world.

4.2. NATO'S NEW STRATEGIC CONCEPT 2022: RESPONDING TO THE THREATS OF RUSSIA'S WAR AGAINST UKRAINE AND THE CHALLENGES OF THE POST-CONFLICT WORLD ORDER

The content of NATO's new Strategic Concept, adopted in 2022, is based on the key principle of the Alliance's updated philosophy, which is to assert its role as the main guarantor of security, stability and predictability of the Euro-Atlantic space, which is of particular importance in the context of strategic competition and the formation of the international security environment after Russia's war against Ukraine. At the same time, the document envisages a significant increase in the influence of this military-political bloc on ensuring a sustainable world order, which is achieved through deepening cooperation with strategic partners, strengthening internal unity and political cohesion of member states, as well as adaptation to new challenges posed by Russia's aggressive actions and other global threats²⁸. When developing new strategic guidelines, NATO experts sought to maintain continuity with the basic tasks defined in the 2010 Lisbon Concept, which include collective defense, crisis management readiness, and expanding cooperation with partners outside the Alliance, but in the current environment, these tasks are taking on a new meaning due to the need to counter hybrid and unconventional threats that have arisen as a result of Russian aggression.

One of the central elements of the modernization of NATO's strategic approaches is the improvement of the political mechanism of interaction between member states, which involves increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of collective decision-making in key areas of activity, such as crisis response, deterrence of aggression and maintenance of global stability. The strategic goal of the Alliance for the next decade is to "guarantee collective defense against all threats from all directions", as stated in NATO's official documents of 2022, which requires the implementation of a number of interrelated tasks: from improving mechanisms for political consultation and training to

²⁷ North Atlantic Treaty Organization, *NATO's response to Russia's invasion of Ukraine (2025)*. https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_192648.htm

²⁸ V. V. Makedon, O. H. Kholod and L. I. Yarmolenko, "Model for assessing the competitiveness of high-tech enterprises based on the formation of key competencies", *Academic Review* vol. 2, no. 59 (2023): p. 75–89. DOI:10.32342/2074-5354-2023-2-59-5

developing defense capabilities, increasing resilience to hybrid threats, maintaining the West's technological advantage over potential competitors such as Russia or China, and countering destabilizing factors affecting the world. In this context, the new version of the Strategic Concept emphasizes three main areas of activity, deterrence and defense, crisis prevention and conflict resolution, and the development of cooperative security through partnerships, which is especially important in the context of the need to respond to Russia's aggressive policies and its attempts to undermine international stability²⁹.

The continuity with previous strategic documents can be seen in the significant attention to "asymmetric" threats to the security of the Euro-Atlantic region, among which terrorism occupies a special place, as stated in the text: "Non-state armed groups, including transnational terrorist networks and state-sponsored actors, continue to exploit conflict and weak governance to recruit and expand their influence." The list of potential dangers also includes illegal migration, the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction, climate degradation, limited access to resources, international crime and piracy, as well as instability in the "global South", particularly in the Middle East and North Africa, which has only been exacerbated by the war in Ukraine and its geopolitical consequences. At the same time, countering non-military threats, such as cyberattacks, disinformation and propaganda, which are actively used by Russia, has become a new priority, reflecting the realities of the post-conflict world, and the document emphasizes that "new technologies are changing the nature of conflicts and becoming key arenas of global competition"³⁰.

When planning NATO's activities for the next decade, considerable attention is paid to expanding the alliance's role in addressing energy and environmental issues, which is being implemented, in particular, through the Science for Peace and Security program, which provides for the introduction of environmentally friendly technologies in the military sphere, as well as the creation of a system to counter biogenic threats, which has become especially relevant after the COVID-19 pandemic and Russia's possible use of such means in hybrid warfare. In response to cyberattacks and other manifestations of hybrid aggression that may come from states like Russia, the document envisages the possibility of activating Article 5 of the Washington Treaty, as well as strengthening consultation mechanisms for rapid response to crisis situations, which should strengthen the unity of the alliance in the face of current challenges caused by the war in Ukraine and broader strategic competition with autocratic regimes.

²⁹ E. Michaels and M. Sus, (2024). *Id.*

³⁰ NATO, *Washington Summit Declaration* (NATO, Brussels, 2024). https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/official_texts_227678.htm.

4.3. NATO'S RESPONSE TO GEOSTRATEGIC CHALLENGES AND ESCALATING THREATS FROM RUSSIA AND CHINA: TRANSFORMING THE SECURITY STRATEGY

One of the key directions of updating NATO's strategic vision in the new geopolitical reality was the realization of radical changes in the international security sphere caused by the resumption of a large-scale confrontation between the Alliance and the Russian Federation, which after 2014, and especially after the beginning of full-scale aggression against Ukraine, became a determining factor in the transformation of the Euro-Atlantic security space. Since then, the main focus of the threats and challenges in the Alliance's strategic documents has been on Russia's aggressive foreign policy and military behavior, which is seen as the main obstacle to stabilizing the situation on the continent, normalizing dialogue between countries and ensuring the predictable development of the global security system.

NATO's strategic approach to the Russian Federation is based on a combination of tools for targeted political dialogue and a powerful deterrence system, which includes strengthening defense capabilities, a coordinated sanctions policy, and eliminating disagreements between the Alliance member states on the scope and mechanisms of response to Russian aggression. Interaction between NATO and the European Union plays a significant role in ensuring this course, which is gaining a qualitatively new meaning in the context of the need to consolidate efforts in military, sanctions, information and cybersecurity³¹.

A decisive catalyst for changes in NATO's strategic thinking was Russia's war against Ukraine, which began in February 2022 and forced the Alliance's governing institutions to quickly review previous formats of cooperation with Russia. This resulted in the adoption of a set of measures to strengthen the Alliance's eastern flank, expanding its military presence in Central and Eastern Europe, in particular through the deployment of additional rapid response contingents and the creation of new multinational units in Bulgaria, Romania, Hungary, and Slovakia. By the summer of 2022, the number of U.S. troops in Europe reached 100,000, and the scale of the Alliance's exercises in the east exceeded the levels of the Cold War³².

NATO's new Strategic Concept 2022 clearly identifies the Russian Federation as a source of multidirectional threats, from traditional military expansion to the use of hybrid instruments of influence, including information destabilization, cyberattacks, and undermining international law. The termination of the partnership with Russia and its official positioning as an adversary reflects the depth of the evolution of the conceptual foundations of the Alliance, which is reorienting itself to a new model of collective defense adapted to the conditions of direct confrontation with authoritarian regimes^{33, 34}.

³¹ G. Grgić, (2024). *Id.*

³² J. Subotic, (2023). *Id.*

³³ G. Bou Serhal and A. Alkhaja, (2024). *Id.*

A priority has been the consistent strengthening of defense capabilities on NATO's eastern flank, which involves the integrated interaction of conventional and nuclear forces, as well as the formation of a new command and control architecture, such as from rear structures in Germany to operational centers in Poland, Romania, Hungary, and the United States. At the same time, there has been a rethinking of the training of the armed forces, which are now focused on large-scale high-intensity combat operations with an enemy equal to the Alliance in terms of military potential.

Significant emphasis is also placed on information confrontation, with special strategic communication units, centers of excellence for countering disinformation, and institutions responsible for monitoring cyber threats and protecting critical infrastructure being created. At the same time, the implementation of long-term military assistance programs for Ukraine continues, aimed not only at supporting defense capabilities but also at ensuring full interoperability with NATO in the future.

Particularly noteworthy is the change in the strategic balance in the Asia-Pacific region, which has resulted in a gradual expansion of NATO's geopolitical focus beyond the traditional Euro-Atlantic area. For the first time at the level of official doctrine, in the Strategic Concept 2022, China was recognized as a factor that threatens the interests and values of the Alliance. Although these challenges are mainly non-military in nature and are related to information influence, technological dominance and economic pressure, the growing cooperation between China and Russia is a concern for NATO in the context of the risk of destroying the rules-based international order³⁵.

Despite the declared readiness for a selective dialogue with China, the Alliance's key goal remains to strengthen its resilience to hybrid influence, in particular through the creation of structures to monitor Sino-Russian military and political cooperation. At the same time, mechanisms are being developed to respond promptly to Beijing's possible asymmetric actions, which creates conditions for the formation of a new, globalized strategic thinking within NATO.

4.4. NATO'S STRATEGIC PLANNING IN A LONG-TERM COMPETITION: PRIORITIES, CONSTRAINTS, AND PRAGMATISM IN THE POST-WAR WORLD ORDER

The key advantage of NATO's new strategic model is its long-term and principled nature, which does not simply respond to short-term subjective features of political processes or military logic, but aims to create a stable basis for the development of the Western coalition's policy and strategy in the context of the transformation of the global

³⁴ H. Sytnyk, M. Orel, V. Ivanova and Y. Taran, "Conceptual understanding of the relationship between political and administrative processes in the context of social systems security", *Cuestiones Políticas* vol. 40, no. 74 (2022): p. 631–647. DOI:10.46398/cuestpol.4074.34

³⁵ A. Mossalanejad, "Ukraine Crisis and Iran's Balancing Regional Role in International Competitions", *Journal of Iran and Central Eurasia Studies* vol. 7, no. 1 (2024): p. 81-94. <http://doi.org/10.22059/jices.2024.371423.1062>

order, which has been significantly affected by Russia’s aggressive actions against Ukraine. Although this model is not without its practical shortcomings, which may complicate its implementation in the short term, it allows us to outline the strategic boundaries of the alliance, which become clearer through the prism of long-term planning aimed at countering Russia as the main destabilizing factor in the current international security environment. To do this, it is proposed to adapt the existing model of the West’s foreign policy strategy, which largely echoes previous approaches, but at the same time takes into account new realities, in particular the concept formulated by Anthony Cordesman, a respected expert from the International Institute for Strategic Studies (CSIS), who emphasized the “priorities” of strategic planning as a crucial element of American policy in the context of global competition³⁶ (Table 1).

Table 1. NATO’s Strategic Planning in a Long-Term Competition: Key Priorities, Goals and Challenges

Priority	Description.	Objective	Limitations
Adapting to a real threat	Assessment of Russia’s economic and military capabilities in view of the war	Creating a cost-effective counteraction structure	Reassessing Russia’s potential
Strengthening the eastern flank	Expanding presence and interoperability with Ukraine	Deterring aggression and supporting partners	Limited resources of member states
Countering hybrid threats	Developing cyber defense and countering disinformation	Increasing resilience to unconventional challenges	Different national priorities
Balance of global and regional goals	Attention to competition with China alongside European stability	Maintaining leadership in a multipolar world	Allocation of resources between regions
Flexible short-term planning	Annual review of strategies to adapt to	Ensuring efficiency and realism in the	Risk of underestimating long-

³⁶ The geopolitical implications of Russia’s invasion of Ukraine (Australian Strategic Policy Institute, 2022). <https://www.aspi.org.au/report/geopolitical-implications-russias-invasion-ukraine>

	changes	face of unpredictability	term threats
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Source: compiled by the author on the basis of Australian Strategic Policy Institute³⁷

These priorities indicate the formation of a new concept of the use of military force in the United States, which is of direct importance for NATO's future strategy in the Ukrainian theater of operations, where Russia's war against Ukraine has become a catalyst for rethinking approaches to deterrence and defense, although this concept has not yet been finalized in legislation. It is important to emphasize that these principles, as noted by E. Cordesman, are aimed at avoiding vague and overly ambitious interpretations of the US military strategy, especially given that the European Union countries are increasingly forming their own, relatively autonomous strategic positions, which complicates coordination within the alliance after the beginning of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict. The first key aspect of this model is the need to adapt the strategy to the real scale of the Russian threat, which implies a comprehensive assessment of Russia's economic and military capabilities, its reaction to the war in Ukraine, and the long-term consequences of this aggression, with an emphasis on creating a cost-effective countermeasure structure that does not seek to solve all problems at once, but focuses on pragmatic goals such as supporting Ukraine and deterring further escalation³⁸.

The second principle emphasizes that NATO should not try to solve all the problems related to the conflict in Ukraine or the broader security situation in Europe, but should focus on the most practical tasks, such as strengthening the defense capabilities of the Alliance's eastern flank or countering hybrid threats from Russia, while recognizing that member states' resources are limited and cannot cover all possible areas at once. This implies a rational approach to the distribution of efforts that takes into account both the national interests of individual NATO states and the collective needs of the alliance, avoiding overestimation of Russian capabilities and not wasting resources on secondary programs, which became especially evident after Russia demonstrated its real, not perceived, military capabilities in the war against Ukraine. The third priority focuses on optimizing NATO's military policy, adapting it to the needs of modern development and the real scale of the threat, where instead of inflated intelligence estimates that exaggerated Russia's strength until 2022, a rational approach is proposed that takes into account both the need to respond effectively to military challenges and the balancing act with civilian costs, which is critical to maintaining support for the Alliance in member countries³⁹.

³⁷ Australian Strategic Policy Institute, 2022. *Id.*

³⁸ A. Gheciu and S. von Hlatky, (2024). *Id.*

³⁹ P. García-Berdoy and C. Samitier, *NATO's strategy after 75 years of adaptation* (LLYC, 2024). <https://lyc.global/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/NATOs-strategy-after-75-years-of-adaptation-1.pdf>

Finally, the fourth aspect combines long-term goals with the need for flexible short-term planning, because, as Cordesman notes, attempts to forecast strategy for many years ahead in the current environment, when the war in Ukraine and rapid technological changes are constantly adjusting reality, are risky, so effective planning should be based on annual review of priorities and be prepared for unforeseen events. All of this together forms an approach in which NATO plays a central role in shaping the world order after Russia's war against Ukraine, balancing deterrence against the aggressor, support for partners such as Ukraine, and adaptation to the new conditions of strategic competition, where cost-effectiveness, pragmatism and flexibility are crucial to the Alliance's success in confronting global challenges.

4.5. INSTITUTIONALIZING NATO'S STRATEGIC FLEXIBILITY: BALANCING RESOURCE PRAGMATISM, GLOBAL LEADERSHIP, AND RESPONSE TO THE WAR IN UKRAINE

A feature of modern strategic thinking within the Western military-political coalition led by NATO is a gradual shift away from an ideologized approach to assessing international threats in favor of a more pragmatic, functional and economically balanced planning model based not on rhetorical escalation or demonstration of force, but on a rational analysis of real capabilities, current resources and priorities within the existing security architecture. This analytical approach, developed by leading Western experts in the field of defense and international security, envisages the creation of a flexible model of short-term strategic planning, focused not on the total solution of all problems, but on achieving realistic goals through the effective use of existing instruments of deterrence, rapid response and optimization of military presence.

This model is based on the realization that NATO's military strategy should not absolutize the threat posed by the Russian Federation or create the illusion that it can be completely neutralized through large-scale rearmament or political pressure, but instead focuses on a flexible balance between short-term tactical solutions and long-term infrastructure projects that both meet real security challenges and do not overburden the financial systems of Allies. This strategic logic, which combines elements of the "war of resources" and the "war of endurance", was partially implemented in NATO's decisions of 2023-2024, when, in parallel with the launch of large long-term infrastructure modernization programs, short-term operational measures were taken to strengthen support for Ukraine and deter potential escalation by Russia⁴⁰.

At the same time, there is an obvious contradiction between strategic documents and political rhetoric that dominated the information space in late 2023 and early 2024.

⁴⁰ H. Hardt, "NATO after the invasion of Ukraine: How the shock changed alliance cohesion", *International Politics* (2024). DOI:10.1057/s41311-024-00629-x

Against the backdrop of temporary failures of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, particularly in the context of offensive actions, NATO countries stepped up their public support for Kyiv, using the rhetoric of uncompromising solidarity, while more restrained and pragmatic decisions were made at the level of strategic centers, based on an objective analysis of resource capabilities and constraints. From this point of view, the growth of public confrontation on the part of Western leaders can be seen as an element of political tactics aimed at preserving the internal unity of the Alliance and signaling resolve to the Russian leadership in order to encourage it to conclude a truce on terms favorable to the West⁴¹. An in-depth analysis of NATO's policy on the Russian-Ukrainian war reveals a multidimensional structure of the coalition, which includes not only 32 Allies and EU members, but also other partner states, including neutral countries, as well as a number of non-state actors such as think tanks, transnational corporations, and defense companies, which form a wide range of influence on military policy, financing, and the supply of defense technologies⁴².

The uneven distribution of power in NATO has allowed Europe to benefit from American protection while keeping its own defense spending significantly lower than the United States as a percentage of GDP, making it easier to finance social programs. While not all NATO allies have cut back on defense, many have done so despite the opportunity to spend more (Figure 1).

Against this backdrop, the overall effectiveness of the Western coalition's strategy in 2024 largely depends on the coherence of actions between these actors, as well as on NATO's ability to conduct adaptive strategic planning in the face of unpredictable combat dynamics⁴³.

⁴¹ A. Mazurkiewicz, (2024). *Id.*

⁴² V. V. Makedon, O. H. Kholod and L. I. Yarmolenko, (2023). *Id.*

⁴³ J. Kinninmont and I. Werenfels, *Regaining NATO's southern neighbours: the alliance should seize the opportunity to jointly reshape southern partnerships* (Berlin: Stiftung Wissenschaft und Politik - SWP- Deutsches Institut für Internationale Politik und Sicherheit, 2024). DOI:10.18449/2024C25

Figure 1. Defense spending by NATO member states as a percentage of GDP at the end of 2022⁴⁴

The key challenge for the Western strategy was that the initial plan of the United States and its allies, which was to inflict economic, financial, and military blows on Russia during the first half of 2022, did not bring the expected result: the sanctions pressure was not destructive enough, the Russian economy adapted, and the country's military-industrial complex was able not only to maintain combat capability but also to increase production. In this situation, Washington, seeking to maintain its global leadership and at the same time send a signal to China that it is ready to respond to challenges, found itself in need of a revision of its strategic line. On the one hand, the United States needs to demonstrate power to assert its status as a security guarantor in the face of strategic competition, especially in the Asia-Pacific region; on the other hand, the available resources and political fatigue of its allies limit their ability to sustain a long-term military confrontation in Eastern Europe⁴⁵.

The current stage of NATO's strategic evolution, which was clearly manifested during the anniversary summit in Washington, marks not just a continuation of the previously chosen course, but the actual institutionalization of already established practices, policies and security strategies, which, in turn, is intended to demonstrate the irreversibility and consistency of the Alliance's transformational trajectory in the face of dynamic international turbulence. The methodology of "strategic posturing" currently used by NATO is not only aimed at protecting the organization from potential internal or external challenges, but also serves as a tool to strengthen its presence in key conflict zones that determine the global security configuration of the 21st century.

Given the priority of the European direction in the light of Russia's full-scale war against Ukraine, as well as the growing geostrategic importance of the Indo-Pacific region, the Alliance has significantly narrowed the list of thematic emphases, leaving

⁴⁴ R. Menon, *Reconfiguring NATO: The case for burden shifting* (Defense Priorities, (2022). <https://www.defensepriorities.org/explainers/reconfiguring-nato/>

⁴⁵ H. Chae, (2024). *Id.*

out a number of other pressing issues, including the ongoing Palestinian-Israeli conflict. This limitation was partly due to the position of Turkey, whose President Recep Tayyip Erdogan openly opposed any form of rapprochement between NATO and Israel before a sustainable and just peace in Palestine was achieved. As a result, most delegations decided to move the discussion of relations with Israel to a bilateral format, and the mention of the Middle East in the final declaration of the summit was minimal, limited to one paragraph out of 38 and fitted into the framework of the general, value-neutral format of the Mediterranean Dialogue, which provides for only symbolic interaction with the countries of the region⁴⁶.

However, in the context of strengthening NATO's institutional presence in the Southern Mediterranean, the Allies reached a consensus on the establishment of a special representative of the Alliance in this area, as well as the opening of a Liaison Center in Jordan, which allows for the maintenance of a regional presence without direct political interference.

The final part of the summit was devoted to internal organizational issues, including the election of a new NATO Secretary General. Former Dutch Prime Minister Mark Rutte was nominated for the post, whose political experience, authority and pragmatism are expected to help Brussels maintain the necessary balance between the Alliance's European vision and its Atlantic component in the next decade. Regardless of the challenges that the Alliance may face in the coming years, NATO is steadily approaching the conventional "fourth age" of its organizational history, as a symbolic limit of political maturity, which, unlike biological aging, is not manifested in decline, but in the need to update its forms of activity and increase efficiency in response to new global threats⁴⁷.

Despite the significant number of crises that NATO has already experienced in more than seven decades of existence, the Alliance has not only remained relevant since the end of the Cold War, but, on the contrary, has received a new justification for its mission (*raison d'être*) in the context of escalating international instability, growing authoritarian threats and strategic revisionism on the part of Russia. Strengthening institutional capacity, expanding functional tasks and doubling the number of members from 16 to 32. The Alliance demonstrates political flexibility, resilience, and the ability to adapt to changes in the international security environment⁴⁸.

The anniversary summit in Washington once again confirmed the determination of NATO member states, in particular those in North America and Europe, to continue

⁴⁶ NATO, *NATO's response to Russia's invasion of Ukraine* (NATO, 2025). https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_192648.htm

⁴⁷ V. Nadkarni, P. D'Anieri, S. Kerr, G. Sharafutdinova, X. Pu, D. M. Ollapally, P. Velasco Junior, C. Moore and A. Divsallar, "Forum: The Russia-Ukraine War and Reactions from the Global South", *The Chinese Journal of International Politics* vol. 17, no. 4 (2024): p. 449-489. DOI:10.1093/cjip/poae021

⁴⁸ NATO Defense College Foundation, "NATO 2024: Beyond the 75th anniversary" (NATO Defense College Foundation, 2025). https://www.natofoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/NDCF-NATO-2024_web.pdf

their strategic investment in the Alliance as a key instrument of collective security. Although some long-term issues remained outside the scope of the final decisions, the leaders agreed on the need to implement the decisions of previous summits, to address existing gaps in the operational response system, to improve the material and technical base and to strengthen NATO's strategic command. Among the announced tasks are ensuring holistic defense planning, deepening the integration of the armed forces of member states, and increasing the level of coordination between the political, diplomatic and military structures of the Alliance.

Thus, NATO's new strategy should be adaptive, resource-efficient and targeted, rather than globally universal; it should take into account both the limited political will of individual member states and the diversity of positions across the spectrum of Western coalition members. In this reality, NATO's place as a leading actor in international security lies not only in formal leadership, but also in its ability to maintain a strategic model that combines political solidarity, military flexibility, and long-term adaptation to changes in the global security landscape.

5. DISCUSSION

The results of the study indicate a profound evolution of NATO's strategic identity in the new geopolitical reality shaped by Russia's war against Ukraine. This confirms the opinion of researchers such as Chae⁴⁹, Marrone and Muti⁵⁰, Gheciu and von Hlatky⁵¹, who believe that the conflict in Ukraine has become a catalyst for not only political but also doctrinal changes in the Alliance, finally cementing its role as a key player in global security that goes beyond NATO's interests. Although our results partially overlap with the position of Tardy et al.⁵², Blessing et al.⁵³, Michalski et al.⁵⁴ on NATO as a security focal point, we offer a different interpretation: The Alliance acts not as a passive guarantor of security, but as an active architect of a new strategic order that shapes norms, models of interaction, and the future security architecture in a multipolar environment.

A key aspect of our study is the institutionalization of NATO's strategic flexibility in response to challenges from Russia and China. This differs from the traditional approaches described by Brunk and Hakimi⁵⁵, who warned of the risks of over-globalization of the Alliance's mission. Instead, we argue that NATO's strategic flexibility is a tool for balancing global influence and internal cohesion. This is reflected

⁴⁹ H. Chae, (2024). *Id.*

⁵⁰ Marrone and Muti, *NATO's Future*.

⁵¹ A. Gheciu and S. von Hlatky, (2024). *Id.*

⁵² T. Tardy, H. Hardt, A. Pannier and C. Kasapoglu, (2022). *Id.*

⁵³ J. Blessing, K. Kjellström Elgin and N. M. Ewers-Peters, (2021). *Id.*

⁵⁴ A. Michalski, D. Brommesson and A.-M. Ekengren, (2024). *Id.*

⁵⁵ I. W. Brunk and M. Hakimi, (2022). *Id.*

in the concept of “strategic fixing” that describes institutional mechanisms for deterrence, adaptation, and leadership in confronting authoritarian regimes.

Unlike Subotic⁵⁶ and Michta⁵⁷, who consider NATO’s cooperation with the Global South as a secondary topic, we consider it a key challenge that requires a rethinking of the concept of collective security. The Alliance’s global leadership is based not only on military power or technology, but also on a normative component – the spread of democratic values, legal standards and new formats of security cooperation, such as NATO+, which is explored in more detail in Michaels and Sus⁵⁸. Regarding the update of the NATO Strategic Concept 2022, many researchers^{59, 60, 61} interpret it mainly as a reaction to Russian aggression. However, our analysis shows that the document is the result of a multi-level dialogue between governments, experts, and institutions that has shaped a new system of strategic planning based on four principles: prioritization of goals, adaptation to resource constraints, flexible planning, and a combination of short- and long-term approaches. These conclusions are complemented by the scholarly position of Gheciu and von Hlatky⁶², who point to a pragmatic turn in Western policy, but do not explain how the Alliance integrates these principles into internal processes.

Comparison with constructivist approaches^{63, 64} provides a framework for deepening the understanding of NATO’s identity. Our study adds a dynamic element to this paradigm by showing that the Alliance’s strategic identity is shaped by political interests, external challenges, and elite discourse. We emphasize strategic consensus as a mechanism for legitimizing change, which does not just fix positions but actively constructs a new reality, including concepts such as “hybrid resilience”, “institutionalized flexibility”, and “predictable interaction”.

The findings challenge overly optimistic assessments of NATO’s internal cohesion^{65, 66}, as real-world decision-making processes reveal significant divisions due to financial and political factors. In this context, we propose pragmatism as a unifying principle that compensates for the lack of full agreement through clear functional tasks. The practical contribution of the study is the conceptualization of “strategic capture of

⁵⁶ J. Subotic, (2023). *Id.*

⁵⁷ A. A. Michta, (2025). *Id.*

⁵⁸ E. Michaels and M. Sus, (2024). *Id.*

⁵⁹ T. Tardy, H. Hardt, A. Pannier and C. Kasapoglu, (2022). *Id.*

⁶⁰ Allied Command Transformation, *Id.*

⁶¹ P. Samson, S. Y. Kalash, N. Zivkovic, T. Forrest and B. Momani, (2024). *Id.*

⁶² A. Gheciu and S. von Hlatky, (2024). *Id.*

⁶³ J. Blessing, K. Kjellström Elgin and N. M. Ewers-Peters, (2021). *Id.*

⁶⁴ G. Grgić, (2024). *Id.*

⁶⁵ A. Mazurkiewicz, (2024). *Id.*

⁶⁶ V. Nadkarni, P. D’Anieri, S. Kerr, G. Sharafutdinova, X. Pu, D. M. Ollapally, P. Velasco Junior, C. Moore and A. Divsallar, (2024). *Id.*

achievements” as a mechanism for stabilizing transformational changes in NATOJ, which helps to better understand the logic of creating new institutional structures (Centers of Excellence, rapid response missions, regional coordination centers). In contrast to formal approaches, we identify informal mechanisms of adaptation based on interaction practices, communication patterns, and the alignment of strategic goals at different levels.

CONCLUSION

6.

Research has shown that NATO’s strategic identity is being shaped and changed by the security challenges posed by Russia’s full-scale war against Ukraine. This process is the result of multilevel cooperation between governments, think tanks and international organizations, which allows the Alliance not only to effectively adapt to changes in the security environment, but also to participate in the formation of a new system of global order based on the principles of collective leadership and ideological unity.

The author outlined the factors of NATO’s new Strategic Concept 2022, which emphasizes a comprehensive approach to multidimensional threats and strategic continuity. Its main innovation is to rethink the Alliance’s priorities in the light of hybrid warfare, technological change and the transformation of global security, integrating elements of strengthening internal cohesion, developing partnerships and increasing operational readiness for new challenges.

The study of NATO’s new strategy on threats from Russia and China shows a shift to an active deterrence strategy, in particular through an increased military presence on the eastern flank, modernization of command and control systems and development of mechanisms to counter hybrid threats, which focuses the direction of changes in the Alliance’s doctrine towards strengthening collective defense in the context of strategic confrontation with authoritarian regimes.

It is proved that NATO’s strategic planning in the context of global competition is based on the rational use of resources, adaptation to real threats and balancing between military and civilian needs in order to systematically create and develop a flexible model of action that takes into account the capabilities of the Allies and ensures the stability of the Alliance in the face of continued global instability.

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